

DATA COLLECTION TOOL FOR IDENTIFICATION AND ANALYSIS OF DRUG-DRUG INTERACTIONS AND ADVERSE DRUG EVENTS IN PEOPLE WITH ACUTE CORONARY SYNDROME

1. DEMOGRAPHIC AND CLINICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF PARTICIPANTS

Initials: _____
 Medical record number: _____
 Study ID: _____
 Sex: 0()Male 1 ()Female
 Age: _____ years old.
 Date of hospitalization: ____/____/____
 Discharge date: ____/____/____
 Diagnosis: 0()Unstable angina 1()ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI)
 2()Non-ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI)
 Type of treatment: 0()Clinical 1()Angioplasty 2()Coronary Artery Bypass Graft Surgery (CABG)
 Outcome: 1()Hospital discharge 2()Death

2. PRESCRIPTION

Drug name	Dosage	Frequency	Route of administration

3. POTENTIAL DRUG-DRUG INTERACTIONS IN PRESCRIPTION

Drug-drug interaction	Classification	Mechanism	Database	Documentation

4. PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS

Collection date									
Blood pressure									
Heart rate									
Respiratory rate									
Electrocardiogram									

5. LABORATORY TEST RESULTS

Collection date							
Platelets							
Hemoglobin							
International Normalized Ratio (INR)							
Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (APTT)							
Creatinine (serum)							
Urea (serum)							
Sodium (serum)							
Potassium (serum)							
Aspartate Aminotransferase (AST)							

Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT)						
Bilirubin (serum)						
Creatine phosphokinase (CPK)						
Blood glucose (fasting)						
Thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH)						
Tetra iodothyronine (T4)						
Total cholesterol						
Low-density lipoprotein (LDL)						
High-density lipoprotein (HDL)						
Triglycerides						

6. ADVERSE EVENTS

- 1() Arrhythmia
- 2() Bradycardia
- 3() Atrioventricular block
- 4() Bronchospasm
- 5() Cardiotoxicity
- 6() Convulsion
- 7() Constipation
- 8() Respiratory depression
- 9() Central Nervous System Depression
- 10 () Stomach discomforts
- 11() Extrapyramidal effects
- 12() Thromboembolism
- 13() Pharmacodermia
- 14() Hepatotoxicity
- 15() Hyperglycemia
- 16() Hypoglycemia
- 17() Hypertension
- 18() Hypotension
- 19() Postural hypotension
- 20() Hyperlipidemia
- 21() Hyperkalemia
- 22() Hypokalemia
- 23() Hyponatremia
- 24() Hematuria
- 25() Digitalis intoxication
- 26() Nephrotoxicity
- 27() Neurotoxicity
- 28() Peripheral neuropathy
- 29() Rhabdomyolysis
- 30() QT interval prolongation
- 31() Minor bleeding
- 32() Gastrointestinal bleeding
- 33() Sedation
- 34() Cushing's syndrome
- 35() Neuroleptic Malignant Syndrome
- 36() Serotonergic Syndrome
- 37() Thrombocytopenia
- 38() Other: _____
- 39() Not applicable

7. CAUSALITY

	Adverse event	Suspected drug	Severity ¹	Temporal relationship ²	Naranjo scale ³	Adverse drug reaction classification ⁴
1.						
2.						
3.						
4.						

¹Severity: (0)Serious (1)Moderate (2)Mild (4)Lethal (5)Not applicable

²Temporal relationship: (0)Plausible (1)Implausible

³Naranjo's causality: (0)Definite (1)Probable (2)Possible (3)Doubtful (4)Not applicable

⁴Adverse drug reaction classification: (0)Type A (1)Type B (2)Not applicable

Adverse drug reaction related to drug-drug interaction? 0(____)No 1(____)Yes 2(____)Not applicable

Naranjo Adverse Drug Reaction Probability Scale Worksheet

Question	Yes	No	Do Not Know	Score
1. Are there previous conclusive reports on this reaction?	+1	0	0	
2. Did the adverse event appear after the suspected drug was administered?	+2	-1	0	
3. Did the adverse event improve when the drug was discontinued or a specific antagonist was administered?	+1	0	0	
4. Did the adverse event reappear when the drug was readministered?	+2	-1	0	
5. Are there alternative causes that could on their own have caused the reaction?	-1	+2	0	
6. Did the reaction reappear when a placebo was given?	-1	+1	0	
7. Was the drug detected in blood or other fluids in concentrations known to be toxic?	+1	0	0	
8. Was the reaction more severe when the dose was increased or less severe when the dose was decreased?	+1	0	0	
9. Did the patient have a similar reaction to the same or similar drugs in any previous exposure?	+1	0	0	
10. Was the adverse event confirmed by any objective evidence?	+1	0	0	
Total Score:				

Definite: Total Score ≥ 9

Probable: Total Score 5 to 8

Possible: Total Score 1 to 4

Doubtful: Total Score ≤ 0